

ANALYTICAL PERMEABILITY MODELLING FOR 3D WOVEN REINFORCEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the permeability of 3D woven carbon fibre fabrics is modelled based on geometrical parameters describing the textile architectures. The in-plane permeability is described by superimposing a disturbance, caused by the binder yarns, to the permeability of a regular layered fibre structure. The through-thickness permeability is derived from combining the Hagen-Poiseuille law, describing the stationary flow of a viscous liquid through a porous medium with identical cylindrical pores with given radius and length, with Darcy's law. The equations for the principal permeability values as functions of the fibre volume fraction appear to describe experimental results more accurately than the frequently employed Kozeny-Carman relation.

Keywords: Liquid Composite Moulding, 3D Weave, Fabric architecture, Permeability

INTRODUCTION

Three-dimensionally woven fabrics are particularly suited for the manufacture of thick components, applying Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) technology, and eliminate the need to produce laminates by stacking of multiple thin layers. They consist typically of layers of aligned non-crimp fibres with alternating orientation along the fabric weft and warp direction, and additional binder fibres, which follow paths through the fabric thickness, thus providing toughness and resistance to delamination.

The flow of penetrating liquid matrix resin during impregnation in LCM processes is more complex for thick fibrous structures with potentially complex architectures than for thin structures. In particular, the influence of through-thickness fibres on the permeability is to be considered. Yet information on the permeability of 3D reinforcement textiles is sparse. Experimental data published by Parnas et al. [1] suggest that the in-plane and through-thickness permeabilities of 3D woven fabrics of undisclosed architecture are in the same order of magnitude as those of various 2D fabrics at similar fibre volume fractions. Elsewhere, anecdotal evidence suggests that 3D orthogonal woven fabrics have significantly higher in-plane permeability than 2D fabrics (woven and knitted) at identical fibre volume fraction [2]. Numerical predictions of the in-plane and through-thickness permeability were made by Ngo and Tamma [3] for an orthogonal weave.

Here, the permeability of 3D woven carbon fibre reinforcements is modelled analytically, based on geometrical information on the textile architecture, and characterised experimentally.

MATERIALS

The permeability was studied for the following 3D woven carbon fibre reinforcements:

Fabric 1 is a through-thickness angle-interlock weave with an average superficial density of 1.438 kg/m^2 , comprising 2 layers of aligned $2 \times 12\text{K}$ tows (two 12K tows effectively forming one 24K tow) in the warp direction, 3 layers of aligned 12K tows in the weft direction, offset from layer to layer by half a bundle width, and 6K binder tows, alternating with the $2 \times 12\text{K}$ tows in the warp direction.

Fabric 2 has an average superficial density of 1.465 kg/m^2 and comprises 2 layers of aligned $4 \times 12\text{K}$ tows in the warp direction, 3 layers of aligned 12K tows in the weft direction, 6K through-thickness binder tows in the warp direction, and 6K tows in the warp direction, interwoven with the top and bottom weft layers. The architecture is similar to that of fabric 1. However, on one fabric surface, every fourth weft yarn is pulled under the nearest binder, thus doubling one weft yarn and creating a gap on the surface.

Fabric 3 is an orthogonal weave with an average superficial density of 4.775 kg/m^2 , comprising 6 layers of aligned 12K tows in the warp direction, 7 layers of aligned $2 \times 6\text{K}$ tows in the weft direction, and 1K binder tows, alternating with the warp yarns. The yarns have almost rectangular cross-section with the exception of the top and bottom weft layer, which are slightly rounded due to lateral compression by the binder.

Fabrics 1 and 3 are examples of typical commercial 3D woven fabrics, while fabric 2 may suit specific applications. For geometrical characterisation of the fabrics, the binder yarn density μ describes the number of through-thickness binder yarn loops per surface area. The pattern of binder loops on the fabric surface is defined by a principal direction and two principal linear densities (in orthogonal directions), forming a diagonal tensor. The principal direction, along which the binder loops on the fabric surface show the highest linear density, and the fabric weft direction enclose the angle β . The principal linear densities λ_1 and λ_2 describe the number of loops per length unit in the direction of β and in the perpendicular direction. γ is the angle between the fabric plane and the binder orientation (through-thickness) at a fabric thickness t . The meaning of the parameters is illustrated in Figure 1, and values are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Binder yarn filament count c_f , binder loop superficial density μ , angle β between principal binder pattern direction and fabric weft direction, binder loop linear densities λ_1 and λ_2 (in direction of β and perpendicular), and angle γ between fabric plane and binder axis, measured at a fabric thickness t (one layer).

fabric	c_f	μ / cm^{-2}	β	$\lambda_1 / \text{cm}^{-1}$	$\lambda_2 / \text{cm}^{-1}$	γ	t / mm
1	6K	1.44	-34°	1.8	0.9	25.6°	2
2	6K	0.72	90°	0.7	0.5	23.9°	2
3	1K	10.08	$\pm 45^\circ$	3.2	3.2	90°	5

Figure 1. A, B: micrographic cross-sections of a plaque moulded with one layer of fabric 1, thickness $t = 2$ mm; A: view along warp direction; B: view along weft direction; C: fabric surface (different magnification).

IN-PLANE PERMEABILITY

For a bundle of aligned filaments, the principal permeability values k_1 (parallel to its axis) and k_2 (perpendicular to its axis) are calculated based on the equations derived by Gebart [4]. The permeability \mathbf{K}_i^* of a layer of aligned fibre bundles is determined by the bundle permeabilities and the equivalent permeabilities of the inter-bundle voids. The axial permeability of a layer, calculated by width-weighted averaging, is dominated by the equivalent permeabilities of the voids under the assumption of rectangular cross-section [5]. The transverse permeability of a layer is dominated by the transverse bundle permeability k_2 . For a stack of several layers of aligned fibre bundles, the in-plane permeability \mathbf{K}^* is estimated by thickness-weighted averaging of the layer permeabilities, considering the respective layer orientations. The in-plane permeability \mathbf{K} of a 3D woven fabric, is modelled by superimposing a disturbance $\Delta\mathbf{K}$, describing the influence of the binder yarns, to the permeability \mathbf{K}^* of a regular layered fibre structure. This concept is illustrated schematically in Figure 2. The disturbance $\Delta\mathbf{K}$ has contributions from the reduction of void space between adjacent bundles in each layer, which reduces the local permeability, and the local creation of dimples around the binder loops on the fabric surfaces, which may connect to form flow channels and thus enhance flow locally.

Figure 2. Illustration of modelling strategy for the in-plane permeability of 3D woven reinforcements (example: angle-interlock fabric).

Unlike \mathbf{K}^* , $\Delta\mathbf{K}$, and thus \mathbf{K} , cannot be predicted quantitatively. However, qualitative estimation of the dependence of \mathbf{K} on V_f may be useful for practical applications. Estimation of \mathbf{K}^* is easiest for orthogonal weaves (such as fabric 3), where the fibre bundles have almost perfectly rectangular cross-sections and the dimensions of the voids, the permeability of which [5] dominates \mathbf{K}^* , are linear functions of the fabric thickness t , i.e. of $1/V_f$. The positive contribution to $\Delta\mathbf{K}$ is estimated to be proportional to the thickness of the binder yarn on the fabric surface, which in turn implies a dependence on $1/V_f$. The negative contribution to $\Delta\mathbf{K}$ is assumed to be independent of V_f . Summarising the different contributions, $\mathbf{K}(V_f)$ can be approximated analytically by equations of the type

$$K_{1,2} = d_{1,2} \left(\frac{1}{V_f^2} - \frac{2}{V_f} + 1 \right), \quad (1)$$

where d_1 and d_2 are constants. For fabrics 1 and 2, on the other hand, the principal permeability values are more difficult to describe, in particular due to non-linear dependencies of the void dimensions on the fabric thickness. However, Equation (1) may still serve as an approximate description.

The unsaturated in-plane permeability of the 3D woven fabrics was measured in radial injection experiments at constant injection pressure, as described elsewhere in more detail [6]. The results for the principal permeability values K_1 and K_2 are plotted in Figures 3 to 6 at different fibre volume fractions V_f .

For Fabric 1 (Figures 3, 4), the in-plane permeability is anisotropic. The ratio K_1/K_2 tends to decrease with increasing compression. The orientation of the principal permeability axes is virtually independent of the fibre volume fraction at an angle $\theta = -27^\circ$ (between β and the weft direction). For Fabric 2 (Figures 3, 4), the values of K_1 and K_2 are in the same order as those of fabric 1. Modification of the angle-interlock pattern results in significant reduction of K_2 , while K_1 is not affected. Some of the permeability values show exceptionally high coefficients of variation (standard deviation/mean

value). This observation can be explained by a strong dependence of the flow behaviour on the location of the injection gate relative to the gaps on the fabric surface. The ratio K_1/K_2 decreases strongly with increasing V_f . However, the orientation of the principal flow direction is different than for fabric 1 and, with increasing fibre volume fraction, rotates away from the weft direction. While, at low values of V_f , the injected fluid flows mainly along the gaps on the fabric surface (in weft direction), the gaps are closed with increasing V_f and the influence of the binder yarns and the interwoven yarns on the flow behaviour increases.

Figure 3. Experimental results for K_1 as a function of fibre volume fraction V_f for fabrics 1 and 2.

Figure 4. Experimental results for K_2 as a function of fibre volume fraction V_f for fabrics 1 and 2.

Figure 5. Fabric 3: Principal permeability K_1 as a function of fibre volume fraction V_f .

Figure 6. Fabric 3: Principal permeability K_2 as a function of fibre volume fraction V_f .

The results for Fabric 3, plotted in Figures 5 and 6 suggest that there is a discontinuity in the permeability as a function of V_f . For $V_f < 60\%$, the binder loops on the fabric surfaces are in contact with the tool surfaces, but there may still be gaps between the (straight) weft yarns and the tool surfaces, which facilitate flow. At higher V_f , these gaps are closed by local deformation of the weft yarns, and the fabric is completely compacted. This results in a significant reduction in K_1 and K_2 . The angle θ , which is approximately constant at 0° , indicates higher permeability along the weft direction than along the warp direction.

In Figures 5 and 6, the experimental data for fabric 3 are compared with curves derived from Equation (1), for which $d_{1,2}$ was selected to achieve the best fit to the mean values, and with curves based on a Kozeny-Carman type relation [7],

$$K_{1,2} \propto \frac{(1-V_f)^3}{V_f^2} . \quad (2)$$

The figures suggest that Equation (2) describes slightly steeper curves than Equation (1). At least for K_2 , Equation (1) fits the experimental data in the relevant range $V_f > 60\%$ better than Equation (2).

THROUGH-THICKNESS PERMEABILITY

Through-thickness flow through a 3D woven fabric has two components, flow through the fibre bundles (perpendicular to the axis) and flow through the holes created by local disturbance of the aligned bundles around the binder yarns. In the following, it is assumed that the flow through the holes is more significant than the flow through the bundles.

Stationary flow of a liquid with viscosity η through a porous medium with N identical cylindrical pores with radius r , driven by a pressure difference Δp along the pore length L , is described by the Hagen-Poiseuille law. The effective pore length depends on the fabric thickness t and the angle γ it includes with the fabric plane. The through-thickness channels created by the binder yarns in an actual fabric are neither cylindrical, nor empty as assumed in the Hagen-Poiseuille law. Thus, r corresponds to an equivalent radius, which is a function of the binder filament count c_f , a form factor φ_0 and the filament radius R_f . The parameters μ (which relates N to the surface area), c_f , φ_0 and R_f depend on the fabric architecture and the yarns used, and thus are constant for each fabric. On the other hand, γ is a function of the fabric compression, i.e. the thickness t . This in turn can be expressed as a function of the fibre volume fraction V_f .

Equating the flow velocity according to Hagen-Poiseuille with the Darcy velocity allows the expression

$$K_3 = \frac{\mu \pi c_f^2 R_f^4}{4} \varphi_0^2 (1-V_f)^2 \sin \left(\arctan \frac{S_0}{\rho x V_f} \right) , \quad (3)$$

where S_0 is the fabric superficial density and ρ is the density of the fibre material, to be derived for the through-thickness permeability K_3 .

Figure 7. Through-thickness permeability K_3 as a function of fibre volume fraction V_f .

K_3 was measured in saturated flow experiments at constant flow rate, as described e.g. by Gouley et al. [8]. The experimental values at different fibre volume fractions V_f and curves calculated from Equation (3) are plotted in Figure 7. The factor $\mu\pi c_f^2 R_f^4/4$ was determined from the values of c_f and μ (Table 1), assuming that the filament radius R_f is 3.5×10^{-3} mm for carbon fibres. In the factor $S_0/\rho x$, the constant values of x can be determined from the measured γ at a given t (Table 1). The density of the carbon fibres was assumed to be $\rho = 1750$ kg/m³. The only unknown in Equation (3), the constant ϕ_0 , can be determined for every pair of values (V_f , K_3). The results suggest that ϕ_0 is identical for fabrics 1 and 2 at a mean value of 1.629. For fabric 3, the mean value of ϕ_0 is 2.047, implying that the ratio of the maximum effective void cross-section and the binder yarn cross-section depends on the fabric architecture.

The experimental values of K_3 for fabrics 1 and 2, which comprise virtually identical binder yarns, differ by a factor of 2, reflecting the ratio of the respective values of μ . For fabric 3, the curve of K_3 as a function of V_f is significantly less steep than for fabrics 1 and 2, since the sine function in Equation (3) is constant at a value of 1. Figure 7 also indicates that, for all investigated fabrics, the decrease of K_3 with increasing V_f is less significant than predicted by a Kozeny-Carman type curve as described in Equation (2).

CONCLUSIONS

For three 3D woven carbon fibre reinforcement fabrics with different architectures, the permeability (in-plane and through-thickness) at different fibre volume fractions was studied experimentally. In an analytical model, the in-plane principal permeability values and the orientation of the principal permeability axes are characterised by the dimensions of the inter-bundle voids in each layer, the pattern of the binder yarns and the dimensions of the binder yarns. Flow-enhancing through-thickness channels in the structure of the 3D reinforcement are formed around the binder yarns. The through-

thickness permeability is modelled as a function of the number of binder yarns per surface area, the binder yarn dimensions, and the angle between the binder yarn axis and the fabric plane. The dimensions and angle of the binder yarn and the dimensions of the inter-bundle voids in both fabric directions depend on the fabric compression. Equations for the principal permeability values as functions of the fibre volume fraction appear to describe experimental results more accurately than the frequently employed Kozeny-Carman relation.

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